

Early Efforts Towards LLM-Based Text Generation for Indigenous Languages of Nepal

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Abstract

Nepal is a linguistically diverse country where many indigenous languages are spoken alongside Nepali, yet most remain severely under-resourced for natural language processing (NLP). This work addresses this gap by developing foundational resources for four languages: Nepali, Newari, Tamang, and Maithili. We curated text corpora, implemented and compared tokenization strategies (BPE, WordPiece, and Byte-level BPE), and trained a GPT-style decoder-only language model. The results showed that the BPE and WordPiece tokenizers consistently outperformed the Byte-level BPE tokenizer, indicating their greater suitability for these languages. The model was then evaluated using perplexity (PPL), achieving promising results for Nepali, Newari, and Maithili, with PPL scores of approximately 25–42, while Tamang lagged behind (PPL = 154), primarily due to limited data and shorter sequence lengths. This highlights the potential for further improvements through the collection of larger and higher-quality datasets.

Introduction

Nepal is a land of diversity with rich cultures and linguistics. There are around 124 languages spoken throughout the nation, among which Nepali is the most widely spoken. According to the 2021 National Population and Housing Census conducted by Nepal’s Central Bureau of Statistics, Nepali is the mother tongue of approximately 44.86% of the population, while the remaining 55.14% speak other languages as their first language. Most of these languages are indigenous, spoken by different ethnic communities throughout the country. Despite Nepal’s rich linguistic diversity, adequate language resources and NLP tools are not available for many of its regional languages. To address this challenge, our work focuses on collecting and curating text

datasets, as well as training tokenizers and language models specifically designed for these low-resource languages.

Challenges

Several indigenous languages in Nepal remain primarily oral and lack standardized writing systems; for example, Chepang and Raute are transmitted almost entirely through spoken communication, with little to no formal written documentation. In contrast, some languages, such as Newari, utilize multiple traditional scripts, including Ranjana, Prachalit, and others. Most of these scripts are not yet supported by standard Unicode encoding, which makes their digital representation challenging. As a result, many of these languages are commonly transcribed using the Devanagari script on digital platforms. Accordingly, in this project, we have also adopted Devanagari for all the languages under consideration.

In this project, we focus on four languages: Nepali, Newari, Maithili, and Tamang. These languages span both widely spoken and low-resource categories, each presenting unique linguistic and digital representation challenges. A key obstacle we encountered is the limited availability of publicly accessible datasets for training NLP models. While reasonably sized datasets for Maithili and Nepali have already been created and can be used for a wide range of NLP tasks, resources for Tamang and Newari are extremely limited.

Addressing Data Scarcity

To mitigate this limitation, we compiled a dataset specifically for this project by scraping publicly available online content in Newari, Maithili, and Tamang languages. The dataset is composed mainly of sentence and text pairs collected from news portals. Each pair is of adequate length and maintains a coherent structure, making it well-suited for training NLP models. Table 1 summarizes the size of the datasets created for each language.

Language	Dataset Size
Newari	10,850,234
Maithili	4,266,731
Tamang	176,422

Table 1: Word counts for each language in the dataset

Although relatively small in size compared to other high-resource lan-

guages, this dataset provides a foundation for developing and evaluating NLP systems for these under-resourced languages.¹

Evaluating Tokenizers

We evaluated several widely used tokenization algorithms, including Byte Pair Encoding(BPE) [1, 2], Byte-level BPE [3], and WordPiece [4] to determine the most suitable option for this project. The tokenizers were trained on same dataset used to train the model, with a vocabulary size of 50,000. Special tokens for padding, unknown words, beginning-of-sequence, and end-of-sequence were included to ensure compatibility with model training.

Average tokens per word

We evaluate the average tokens per word for three tokenizers across Nepali, Newari, Maithili, and Tamang languages, as shown in Table 2.

Tokenizers	Nepali	Newari	Maithili	Tamang
BPE	1.15	1.66	1.48	1.98
Byte-level BPE	4.33	4.42	3.58	4.60
WordPiece	1.11	1.48	1.38	1.97

Table 2: Average tokens per word (sample size = 1000)

From Table 2, WordPiece consistently produces the lowest average tokens per word across all four languages, indicating that it generates more compact token sequences. BPE also performs efficiently, with slightly higher averages in some languages. In contrast, Byte-level BPE results in substantially higher token counts. This increase is primarily due to its byte-level representation: each Devanagari character is encoded as multiple bytes in UTF-8, causing words to be split into more tokens than when using character- or subword-level tokenizers [5]. These results highlight the trade-off between tokenizer granularity and token sequence length in morphologically rich languages.

Single token coverage

To compare how effectively different tokenizers represent entire words, we measured the single-token coverage (%) for BPE, Byte-level BPE, and Word-

¹<https://huggingface.co/datasets/SughamKharel/nep-indgns>

Piece across Nepali, Newari, Maithili, and Tamang languages, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Single-token coverage (%) (sample size = 1000)

WordPiece and BPE consistently achieve higher single-token coverage than Byte-level BPE, particularly for Nepali and Newari. This indicates that WordPiece and BPE are more likely to tokenize individual words into a single token, making them more efficient for these languages.

Based on both average tokens per word and single-token coverage, WordPiece is the most suitable tokenizer for this project. It consistently yields low token counts per word while maintaining high single-token coverage across all evaluated languages, achieving an effective balance between efficiency and accuracy for downstream model training. Although Byte-level BPE is often preferred in multilingual settings, its advantages are less relevant here since all languages in this project use the Devanagari script.

Dataset

To build a comprehensive training set, we combined the datasets created during this project with several publicly available datasets. This merged corpus allowed us to improve both the size and diversity of data across all four languages. The datasets were preprocessed by removing all non-Devanagari characters and replacing numerical digits with the <d> token, which improves the model’s training efficiency given its relatively small size.

Publicly available datasets used for this project include *Nepali-Text-Corpus* [6], *GLOT-500* [7], *OSCAR* [8, 9], *Nepali-Tamang-MT-Data* [10]

	Corpus Size			
	Nepali	Newari	Maithili	Tamang
Train	2,000,000	40,361	59,660	10,875
Test	5,000	963	1,005	1,040

Table 3: Corpus size for different languages in train and test splits

Indigenous-eng-translation and *Bharat-NanoBEIR Maithili*. Table 3 reflects the combined size of the datasets after deduplication and preprocessing.

Training

We trained a GPT-like decoder-only Transformer model [11, 3] tailored for autoregressive language modeling tasks. The model consists of 8 transformer layers, each with 12 attention heads, a hidden size of 768, an intermediate size of 3072, and a maximum context length of 512 tokens. The complete architectural configuration is provided in Table 4.

Vocabulary Size	50,000
Context Length	512
Number of Layers	8
Number of Attention Heads	12
Hidden Size	768
Intermediate Size	3072
Activation Function	GELU
Positional Encoding	Learned

Table 4: Model Architecture

The model was trained for a total of 160,000 steps, including a warm-up phase of 5,000 steps. In the initial stage, training was performed for 150,000 steps on the complete dataset, followed by fine-tuning for 10,000 steps using a reduced Nepali dataset (5% of the original) combined with the full datasets of the other languages to address the significant imbalance in dataset sizes. We trained the model with a batch size of 72 and a dropout rate of 0.05. The AdamW optimizer was used with a learning rate of 5×10^{-5} and $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$.

Training was carried out on a single NVIDIA L40S GPU with 48 GB of memory, using float16 mixed-precision to accelerate computation and reduce memory usage.

Evaluation

To assess the performance of our model², we computed perplexity (PPL) scores for each language, both with and without fine-tuning. The results are summarized in Table 5.

Model	Nepali	Newari	Maithili	Tamang
Without Fine-tuning	25.35	41.30	67.92	281.48
With Fine-tuning	27.81	24.55	41.94	154.00

Table 5: Perplexity (PPL) scores for the model with and without fine-tuning

The results in Table 5 present the model’s perplexity (PPL) scores both before and after fine-tuning. The model performed reasonably well on Nepali, Newari, and Maithili, with the lowest PPL observed for Nepali (25.35) and moderate scores for Maithili (67.92) and Newari (41.30). In contrast, the model struggled significantly with Tamang, showing a very high PPL (281.48), likely due to the limited size of its dataset and the short sequence lengths of the available documents. Fine-tuning led to a decent improvement in Newari, Maithili, and Tamang, while Nepali showed minimal change.

Generated Text Samples

We generated text using the fine-tuned model with a temperature of 1 and top-k sampling set to 50 for all prompts.

■ Prompt
■ Model Output

²<https://huggingface.co/SughamKharel/nep-indgns-model>

Nepali

नेपाल सरकारले पाँच वर्षभित्र आर्टिफिशल इन्टेलिजन्स (एआई) क्षेत्रमा कम्तीमा <d>, <d> जनशक्ति तयार गर्ने लक्ष्य राख्दै आर्टिफिशल इन्टेलिजन्ससम्बन्धी नयाँ नीति कार्यान्वयनमा ल्याएको छ । उक्त नीतिले अन्तर्राष्ट्रिय आधारभूत सिद्धान्त र प्रचलनसँग अनुकूल हुने गरी एआईको अनुसन्धान, विकास र प्रयोगलाई " दिशानिर्देश गर्न " नेपालमा एआई नियमन परिषद् स्थापना गर्ने रणनीति लिएको छ । यो नीति अनुसार एआई क्षेत्रलाई तीन वर्षसम्म निरन्तर व्यावसायिक, व्यवस्थित र नियन्त्रित बनाइने छ । यस नीतिले उच्च - स्तरीय एआई अनुसन्धान, विकास, आविष्कार, वितरण तथा नियमन, डाटा सुरक्षा, मूल्यांकन तथा विश्लेषण, बजारीकरण, र दूरसञ्चार पूर्वाधार निर्माण, विश्लेषण तथा परिमार्जन, व्यवस्थापन, मूल्यांकन तथा नियमनको जिम्मासहित उच्चस्तरीय साइबर सुरक्षा अनुगमन आयोग स्थापना गरिने छ । यस आयोगको गठन सन् <d> को फेब्रुअरीमा भएको थियो । आयोग स्थापना गर्नका लागि <d> हजार <d> जनाको आवेदन परेकामा <d> हजार <d> जनाको आवेदन परेको थियो । ...

Newari

मध्यपुर थिमि नगरपालिका – <d> बोडेय् म्हीग निसें बोडेया नांजा:गु निलबाराही प्याखँ पिका:गु दु । दैवी शक्ति व तान्त्रिक विधि कथं स्वन्हु प्यचा तक निलबाराहीया द्य: प्याखँ हुइकेगु याइ । द्य: गणय् झिंगुम्ह द्य:पिं दुथ्याइसा बाजं थाइपिं याना: सछि स्वयां अप्व: मनूत जात्राय् संलग्न जुइगु याइ । अथेहे यल लाय्कू लाय्कूय् च्वंपिं आपालं भैल:, चीद्य:यात जक पचलि याना: <d> इज्च स्वयां अप्व: तक निरन्तर द्य: चा:हिउगु दु । बोडे द्य:यात बासुकीग:या प्रतीक धाइगु परम्परा दु । थौंकन्हय् गणया झिंछम्हेसिनं म्येय् म्येय् प्याखं, धा: हुया बाजं थाइपिं द्य:पिं व द्य: नापला:गु प्याखंयात भैरव धायेगु याना वयाच्वंगु दु । न्हापा न्हापा न्हापा: गंप्याखं थें गणय् ब्वयेधुंका: गणं <d> इज्च तक म्येय् प्याखं ल्हुइ । व न्हापा: (बोडे) या ख्वा:पा: पुया: भैरवया ख्वा:पा: पुया: भैरवयात भैरव धायेगु चलन दु । ...

Maithili

नेपालके सांस्कृतिक आ भाषिक विविधतासँ अइ ठाँमक फिल्म उद्योगकेँ समृद्ध बनेबाक सम्भावना रहलोपर ताहिअनुसार उपलब्धि तँ प्राप्त नईं भेल अछि । नेपाली भाषाबाहेक अन्य स्थानीय भाषामे चलचित्र निर्माणके सङ्ख्या नेपालमे बहुते न्यून छै । फिल्म उद्योग उद्योगमे एक स्थान मात्रमे परैत छै । फिल्मक उद्योगमे तीन सय <d> परिवार (<d> प्रतिशत महिला, आधा पुरुष तथा सात महिला) अछि । एहि उद्योगमे गीत, सङ्गीत तथा नाटकक विधा सेहो उद्योगमे परैत अछूत प्रमाणित भेल अछि, तहिना बाल कलाकार तथा दर्शकक संख्या मात्रमे फिल्मांकनक लेल उल्लेखनीय रहल । विदेशी फिल्म, चलचित्र आ टेलिभिजन सिनेमासभ राष्ट्रिय चलचित्र रजिस्ट्रीमे सूचिकृत होमए के सुविधा प्रदान करौनिहार अछि । ई क्षेत्र मे <d> जना लोग चलचित्रसभ आ एक सिनेमा हल अछीके सँ कम आय रहल अछि । ...

Tamang

च्युम्बा च्युम्बा क्वारक्वारबा मि, क्लुमक्लुम्बा लि, नाप्ले नाप्ले नार्तु, सातान पाराडस्याला डेचिबा स्हाल, डेमा म्राड्बा टम्म डिक्बा तार स्वा थेन वाला वाला ग्राम्बाला डिम्पल म्राड्सि क्यालो क्लाड्बारि इहाच्छा वाड्मुबा बटुवाजुगु । तासाइ डाला तिगाजि । दिम डा सुडकिड तासेला दिमला, थोबाहाडला लि छ्योइग्याम्सि मुबा । डाइ ख्लासि स्यान दोजि । डादा म्राड्सि । मि न्हासि च्यामुबा म्हान्जि । डेसि दोजि । न्हासि म्हान्बारि म्हान्बान मुला? चु तामला छ्याम ड्याजि । डेबाइ थेदा छ्याम दोजि । ड्यासे हाडसे गोदे, हाड्बाकादेनदा सुड्सि क्लाड्बाकादेन ओम । न्हासिमरि डाला काडा क्वाइ ड्यासे क्वाइ? याखार, जे ख्लासि म्हान्बा दोजि । काडसे दोजि । थेला राप, तिगा खाराडरि मुला, थे ह्याड थेरि जे थेन ताड्बाला । डान्ना मुतेबा थेला चेगाइ । डालान म्राड्सि दिम इहान्बा मुबा । थे नोन चु दिमरि डेजि । ...

Conclusion

This study represents an early effort to develop NLP resources for the indigenous languages of Nepal. By building on the limited existing resources, we addressed key challenges in low-resource language settings by creating a dedicated dataset. We evaluated several tokenization methods and found that BPE and WordPiece substantially outperformed Byte-level BPE. Using these resources, we trained a GPT-like decoder-only language model and assessed its performance, observing that Nepali, Newari, and Maithili achieved significantly better results, whereas Tamang lagged due to the limited size of its dataset.

Although this work lays an important foundation, much more research is needed to advance NLP for Nepal’s regional languages. In particular, collecting and expanding datasets remains a key challenge for effectively training LLMs in these languages.

References

- [1] Philip Gage. A new algorithm for data compression. *C Users J.*, 12(2):23–38, 1994.
- [2] Rico Sennrich, Barry Haddow, and Alexandra Birch. Neural machine translation of rare words with subword units. In *Proceedings of the 54th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*, pages 1715–1725, 2016.

- [3] Alec Radford, Jeffrey Wu, Rewon Child, David Luan, Dario Amodei, and Ilya Sutskever. Language models are unsupervised multitask learners, 2019. OpenAI blog.
- [4] Yonghui Wu, Mike Schuster, Zhifeng Chen, Quoc V. Le, Mohammad Norouzi, Wolfgang Macherey, Maxim Krikun, Yuan Cao, Qin Gao, Klaus Macherey, et al. Google’s neural machine translation system: Bridging the gap between human and machine translation. In *arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.08144*, 2016.
- [5] Sander Land and Catherine Arnett. Structured encoding for robust multilingual pretokenization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.24689*, 2025.
- [6] Prajwal Thapa, Jinu Nyachhyon, Mridul Sharma, and Bal Krishna Bal. Development of pre-trained transformer-based models for the nepali language, 2024.
- [7] Ayyoob ImaniGooghari, Peiqin Lin, Amir Hossein Kargaran, Silvia Severini, Masoud Jalili Sabet, Nora Kassner, Chunlan Ma, Helmut Schmid, André Martins, François Yvon, and Hinrich Schütze. Glot500: Scaling multilingual corpora and language models to 500 languages. In Anna Rogers, Jordan Boyd-Graber, and Naoaki Okazaki, editors, *Proceedings of the 61st Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*, pages 1082–1117, Toronto, Canada, July 2023. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [8] Pedro Javier Ortiz Su’arez, Laurent Romary, and Benoit Sagot. A monolingual approach to contextualized word embeddings for mid-resource languages. In *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 1703–1714, Online, July 2020. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [9] Pedro Javier Ortiz Su’arez, Benoit Sagot, and Laurent Romary. Asynchronous pipelines for processing huge corpora on medium to low resource infrastructures. *Proceedings of the Workshop on Challenges in the Management of Large Corpora (CMLC-7) 2019*. Cardiff, 22nd July 2019, pages 9 – 16, Mannheim, 2019. Leibniz-Institut für Deutsche Sprache.
- [10] Binaya Kumar Chaudhary, Bal Krishna Bal, and Rasil Baidar. Efforts towards developing a Tamang Nepali machine translation system. In Pushpak Bhattacharyya, Dipti Misra Sharma, and Rajeev Sangal,

editors, *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Natural Language Processing (ICON)*, pages 281–286, Indian Institute of Technology Patna, Patna, India, December 2020. NLP Association of India (NLPAI).

- [11] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N Gomez, Łukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. Attention is all you need. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 30, 2017.